

Towards a multi-VOC emission reference material with temporally constant emission profile for QA/QC of materials emission testing procedures

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Porous materials impregnated with VOCs as emission reference materials.
- Stable emission over 14 days with at least two materials and *n*-hexadecane.
- Highly reproducible emission profile for activated carbon loaded with toluene.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Emission reference materials (ERMs) are sought after to further control and improve indoor air quality. The impregnation of porous materials with volatile organic compounds (VOCs) is a promising approach to produce ERMs. Different VOCs were used to impregnate various porous materials (mainly zeolites, activated carbons and a metal organic framework). The influence of different methodological parameters and material properties were studied to optimize the impregnation procedure and to find the best material/VOC combination. The impregnation procedure remains quite irreproducible, nevertheless, very good ERM candidates were identified. Two materials (zeolite 4 and AC 1 impregnated with *n*-hexadecane) showed a very stable emission over 14 days (<10 % change). Another material (AC 1 impregnated with toluene) showed a declining emission profile but with a very good in-batch reproducibility and a storage stability of up to 12 months.

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1. Introduction

The indoor environment has a significant influence on human health and a person's perception of well-being. Emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOC) from construction materials and other products used indoors, such as furniture, electronic devices, cleaning agents, etc., constitute a significant source of indoor pollution and result, under certain environmental and occupational conditions, in sensory irritation and health complaints. (Wolkoff et al., 2012; Wolkoff, 2013; Steine-mann, 2015). The VOC concentrations in the indoor air can become further elevated in new or refurbished buildings (ECA, 2012) where the rate of air exchange with fresh ambient air may be limited due to improved energy saving aspects (Müller and Mertes, 2017). A healthy indoor environment can be achieved by controlling the sources and by eliminating or limiting the release of harmful substances into the air. One way is to use materials proven to be low emitting. Meanwhile, a worldwide network of professional commercial and non-commercial laboratories performing emission tests for the evaluation of products for interior use has been established. Therefore, comparability of test results must be ensured. A laboratory's proficiency can be proven by internal and external validation measures that both include the application of suitable reference materials. The emission test chamber procedure according to ISO 16000-9 (ISO, 2023) and EN 16516 (EN, 2020) comprises several steps from sample preparation to sampling of test chamber air and chromatographic analysis. Quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) must therefore be ensured. For this purpose, well-characterised emission reference materials (ERM) that release a known amount of selected VOC when put into an emission test chamber are desirable. It should furthermore be homogeneous, reproducible and stable over a certain period. Several approaches towards such a material can be found in the literature. Cox et al. (2010) described a candidate ERM that is suitable for loading into test chambers but emitted only one specific compound (toluene). Based on this material, a first round robin test was conducted (Howard-Reed et al., 2011). However, due to the high variety of VOCs usually emitted from building materials, furniture and other products used indoors, a broader spectrum of compounds should be covered by a reference material. Nohr et al. (2014, 2015) made a step forward with a multi-VOC ERM based on a water-based lacquer to which a mixture of VOCs was added. After portioned into Petri-dishes the lacquer was cured and could be sent to the user. The material had shown good homogeneity and reproducibility for 5 out of 9 compounds (RSD 5–6 %), with RSDs of 11–19 % for the remaining four compounds (Horn et al., 2018). In the last years, it was successfully applied in several international RRT, showing an improvement of the comparability of the emission chamber testing by the decrease of the mean RSD down to 28 % (Wilke et al., 2021).

However, to fulfil all QA/QC requirements of test standards dealing with emission test chambers (i.a. ISO, 2012a, b, c; EN, 2016; ISO, 2017a, b, 2018; EN, 2019, 2020; ISO, 2020, 2023), such as the determination of the recovery, sources that release the target VOC constantly over time are desirable. The high number of test protocols handling a variety of different material types indicates the necessity of well-characterised ERM ideally adapted to the respective product to be tested. Some attempts towards this goal can be found in the literature. Wei et al. (2012) developed a tool which they called liquid-inner tube diffusion-film-emission (LIFE). It consists of a PTFE vial capped with a membrane and containing the compound of interest (toluene). Toluene from the gas-phase inside the container permeates through the membrane with a specific rate and generates a constant emission rate with less than 3 % change. Salthammer et al. (2017) published another approach of a permeation-controlled formaldehyde reference source. Here, paraformaldehyde as a formaldehyde source is filled into a stainless-steel vessel, which is capped with an insert with a defined opening. By varying the dimensions of the opening the permeation rate can be adjusted. Stable formaldehyde concentrations between 16 and 74 ppb were obtained for at least 22 h.

However, these approaches have not been further developed for the use as a multi-VOC releasing source. The EU-funded research project 20NRM04 MetriAQ aims at the development of a multi-component ERM with a reproducible and temporally constant emission profile over at least 14 days. This shall be reached by using two kinds of reservoir materials that will serve as emission source: 1) porous materials impregnated with the target compound under high pressure with supercritical CO₂ as solvent, and 2) encapsulation of the VOC into a permeable shell material.

In this paper, the results of the work on the porous materials are reported. The approach builds up on preceding work, where sliced thermoplastic polyurethane was impregnated with VOC under high pressure and with supercritical CO₂ as solvent (Richter et al., 2017). The benefit was a much higher source strength compared to the lacquer material of Horn et al. (2018). However, also here the emission rate decreases quite fast between 45 and 93 % within 18 days calculated from the point of time where reproducibility between the batches was obtained (day 10).

The materials tested in this study were zeolites of different Si/Al ratios, activated carbons, and a metal-organic framework (MOF). The optimal preparation parameters are investigated to obtain a material with an emission profile that decreases less than 10 % over at least 14 days. This stability will be of particular importance, when the candidate reference material will be used for intra-laboratory validation exercises, e.g. the determination of the test chamber recovery as prescribed by the respective ISO and EN test standards.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

For the impregnation of the porous materials and the analysis, the following chemical substances were used in this study: carbon dioxide (Linde, 99.995), nitrogen (Linde, 99.9999), helium (Linde, 99.9999), liquid nitrogen (Air Liquide), synthetic air (Linde, free of hydrocarbons), hydrogen (Linde, 99.999), *n*-hexane [110–54-3] (Merck, ≥99), *n*-heptane [142–82-5] (Merck, ≥99), toluene [108–88-3] (J.T. Baker, ≥99.5), 2-ethyl-1-hexanol [104–76-7] (Fluka, 99.6), butyl glycol [111–76-2] (J.T. Baker, ≥99), methyl isobutyl ketone [108–10-1] (MIBK, thermo scientific, 99), 2-methoxyethanol [109–86-4] (Acros, ≥99), cyclohexanone [108–94-1] (Acros, ≥99), butyl acetate [123–86-4] (Merck, ≥99.5), methanol [67–56-1] (Aldrich, 99.9) and *n*-hexadecane [544–76-3] (Acros, 99).

2.2. Porous materials

In Table 1 the porous materials that were impregnated with the target compounds are listed. They belong mainly to the groups of zeolites and activated carbons. A metal-organic framework (MOF) and an aerogel were tested as well. The materials were chosen based on their material properties such as median pore size, polarity, and surface area. Polar materials can be hygroscopic, which can impede the emission under humid conditions. Thus, non-hygroscopic materials are favorable. Further differences can appear in the pore shape, the pore size distribution, the form of the material (e.g., granulate or powder) and the particle size.

2.3. Gas adsorption measurement

Gas sorption is a widely used method for determining the specific surface area and pore size distributions, whereby the amount of an adsorbed gas is measured as a function of the relative pressure of the adsorbent. The porosity and surface area were measured with help of gas adsorption methods using an ASAP 2020 (Micromeritics Instrument Corporation). The isotherms were measured under argon atmosphere at 87 K. Around 50–300 mg of sample was used for each measurement.

Samples were outgassed for 4 h at ambient pressure (under N₂ atmosphere) and at 120 °C (activated carbons) or 350 °C (zeolites) prior to measurement.

Depending on the material different analytical theories were used for the determination. Calculations of the pore sizes were done either from the adsorption or desorption isotherm using the method of Horvath-Kawazoe (activated carbons) and Horvath-Kawazoe with extension of Saito-Foley (zeolites). The specific surface areas were calculated from the adsorption branch of the isotherm using the method of Brunauer, Emmett and Teller (BET).

2.4. Sample preparation/impregnation

The impregnation was carried out in an autoclave (BüchiGlasUster novoclave Typ 3/200 mL, Büchi, Flawil, Switzerland) paired with a cyclone 075 dc stirrer according to the scheme shown in Fig. 1. Prior to the impregnation, the porous materials (Table 1) were dried for 20 h at 120 °C, weighed, and placed into the autoclave. Then the VOC was added. After sealing the autoclave, CO₂ was introduced, then the autoclave was heated which leads to an increase of the internal pressure. During the phase change of the CO₂ to the supercritical state (73.75 bar, 31 °C), the VOC and CO₂ become one phase (Richter et al., 2017). After reaching this point, the stirrer was switched on to ensure that the sample is well flushed by the CO₂/VOC mixture. After 2 min the heating was turned off and the pressure was slowly released.

After the impregnation, the sample was taken out of the autoclave, weighed, and placed into an emission test chamber. For a quick evaluation of the success of the impregnation, the samples were put into a μ -CTE™ (Markes International) (see section 2.5). By default, these chambers are operated with a dry flow of synthetic air. If the re-release of the target component for the respective material met the criteria described in section 2.7, a new batch was prepared and tested in the larger chambers (24 or 270 L) under standardised test conditions with humidified air. Once it had been determined that humidity has a significant impact on the release of VOCs from the porous materials, the screening tests in the μ -CTE™ were also carried out with humidified air.

2.5. Emission test chambers

After the impregnation, samples were taken out of the autoclave and loaded into emission test chambers. Different chamber types were available.

1. A Micro-Chamber/Thermal Extractor™ (μ -CTE™, M-CTE120, Markes International) for the evaluation of the impregnation process. It comprises six chambers (44 mL) which are fed with a dry or humidified flow between 22 and 42 mL min⁻¹ of synthetic air (Air Liquide, free of hydrocarbons) regulated by a mass flow controller (MFC, 4800 Series, BROOKS). The device can be heated up to 120 °C. Because it was observed that it cannot maintain the standard temperature of 23 °C due to the too small difference to the ambient temperature and is therefore subject to fluctuations, a slightly higher chamber temperature of 26 °C was set, which can be controlled with significantly smaller fluctuations.
2. Glass desiccators of 24 L and chambers made of electropolished stainless steel with a volume of 270 L. Both types were operated dynamically under controlled climatic conditions at a temperature of (23 ± 1) °C and a relative humidity at either 0 % (dry air) or (50 ± 5) % according to EN 16516 (EN, 2020). The 24 L and 270 L test chambers are equipped with a ventilator to ensure a homogenous air distribution.

All chambers provided sampling ports for sampling on thermal desorption tubes.

Detailed descriptions of the chamber types can be found elsewhere (Schripp et al., 2007; EN, 2020). Before loading, the chambers were tested for blank values.

2.6. Analysis

The test chamber air was sampled on Tenax® TA tubes (Gerstel, Mülheim, Germany) which were thermally desorbed in a thermal desorption system (TDS 3, Gerstel) and then trapped in a cold injection system (CIS 4, Gerstel), filled with a silanized glass wool liner and connected to a gas chromatograph (GC) 6890 N (Agilent, Santa Clara, USA) coupled to a mass spectrometer (5973 MS, Agilent) for identification and quantification. The gas chromatographic separation was carried out on a DB-5-MS-UI column (Agilent, 60 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μ m) with a constant helium flow (Linde, 99.9999) of 1.5 mL min⁻¹. Thermal desorption of the sampling tube started at 40 °C (initial time 0.5 min) and heated up with 40 °C min⁻¹ to 290 °C (holding time 5 min). The temperature of the transfer line was set at 320 °C and the CIS was set at -100 °C. After finishing the thermal desorption of the tube, the CIS started to heat (equilibration time 0.05 min, initial time 0.1 min) with a heating rate of 12 °C min⁻¹ to 300 °C (holding time 5 min). The analytes were injected with a split of 1:7 into the GC column, and the GC oven program started at 40 °C (holding time 4 min) and heated up with 10 °C

Table 1
Porous materials with relevant material properties used in the study.

Material type	Entry	Material name	Commercial name	Form	Micro pore volume ^a [cm ³ /g]	Total pore volume ^b [cm ³ /g]	Median pore width [nm]	Zeolite type	Surface area [m ² /g]	Si/Al
Zeolite	1	Zeolite 1	FD-107	granules	0.198 ^a	0.432 ^a	0.668 ^a	Y	611 ^b	1.6
	2	Zeolite 2	13X APG	granules	0.223 ^a	0.380 ^a	0.659 ^a	X	603 ^a	1.5
	3	Zeolite 3	3A EPG	granules	- ^c	- ^c	0.3 ^{b, c}	A	- ^c	1.4
	4	Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	powder	0.235 ^a	0.483 ^a	0.687 ^a	H	612 ^a	150
Activated carbon	5	AC 1	C 40/4	pellets or powder	0.389 ^a	0.543 ^a	0.884 ^a	-	1139 ^a	-
	6	AC 2	C 45/4	pellets or powder	0.371 ^a	0.461 ^a	0.855 ^a	-	1019 ^a	-
	7	AC 3	C 47/4	pellets or powder	0.361 ^a	0.441 ^a	0.844 ^a	-	978 ^a	-
Metal organic framework	8	MOF	ZIF-8	pellets	0.663 ^b	-	1.16 ^b	-	1947 ^b	-

^amicro pore volume until 2 nm ($p/p_0 \leq 0.2$).

^btotal pore volume of the measured isotherm ($p/p_0 = 0.99$).

^a the samples were measured in argon at 87 K, the surface area was calculated using BET, pore volume and median pore width calculated using Horvath-Kawazoe (carbons) and HK Saito-Foley (zeolites).

^b taken from literature (Park et al., 2006; Kim et al., 2016).

^c too small for the herein used method.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the impregnation process: (1) the porous material and a proportion of VOC are placed into the autoclave. Then the autoclave is sealed, CO₂ is introduced, and the heating is started. The CO₂ reaches its supercritical point (2, above 73 bar and 35 °C) and the porous material is being impregnated. After a few minutes (3), the pressure and temperature are slowly reduced, and the impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave.

min⁻¹ to 150 °C and then with 8 °C min⁻¹ to 280 °C (holding time 3 min). The MS (transfer line at 300 °C, EI-source at 230 °C and quadrupole at 150 °C) operated in SCAN-mode (m/z 40–550) with a solvent delay of 4 min. Quantification was carried out using calibration curves (6 points, ranging from 20 to 420 ng μL⁻¹ for all substances). The calibration solutions were prepared with highly pure chemicals and methanol as a solvent. One μL of each solution was spiked onto different Tenax® TA tubes, which were then measured with help of the TD-GC/MS. A quality control standard (100 ng) was measured twice a week to guarantee a good performance of the analytical system.

2.7. Investigations of material performance and evaluation of results

After impregnation, 1–2 g of the material was loaded into μ-CTE™ test chambers for screening the emission behaviour (typically for 336–504 h). Air sampling started usually 3–4 days after loading. Sampling was then conducted every second day. The sampling time was 5 min, and the resulting volume was between 0.11 and 0.21 L (μ-CTE™) depending on the respective chamber flow rate. If a material showed good results during screening, a fresh sample of this material (1–2 g) was tested in a 24 L or 270 L emission test chamber due to a better possibility to control the emission test chamber parameters and thus higher reliability of the measurement results. About 1 L (sampling flow rate of 100 mL min⁻¹) of air was sampled from the 24 L and 270 L test chambers. The air change rate n was set at approximately 30–60 h⁻¹ in the μ-CTE™, at 0.4 h⁻¹ in the 24 L, and 0.5 h⁻¹ in the 270 L emission test chambers. For a comparison of the measurement results between the different porous materials and an evaluation of the impact of the process relevant parameters, the mass specific emission rate was used, as this is a normalised parameter.

The SER_m in μg g⁻¹ h⁻¹ is calculated according to Eq. (1), where c_i is the test chamber air concentration of the VOC i in μg m⁻³, L the chamber loading in g m⁻³, n is the air change rate, m the mass of the impregnated material loaded into the chamber, and V_{ch} the test chamber volume in m³.

$$SER_m = c_i \times \frac{n}{L}, \text{ with } L = \frac{m}{V_{ch}} \quad (1)$$

The aim of the project is to develop a temporarily constant-emitting reference material to meet, i. a., the criteria for determining the recovery rate of emission test chambers in accordance with ISO 16000-9 (ISO, 2023), saying that the recovery “of a target VOC can be determined using a VOC source of known specific emission rate in the emission test chamber. [...] Chamber concentrations shall be determined at 72 h after start of the test [...]” That means that the source must be at least stable over this period of time. Preliminary tests have revealed that a much longer stability time would be feasible. Therefore, for this study, a success control was defined saying that the emission profile of the candidate ERM is

constant, when its decrease is less than 10 % over at least 14 days. This stability is expressed as the slope of the emission curve ΔER in percent determined from the point the profile is reaching a stabilised course. The time until this turning point is attained is the ageing phase of the material.

2.8. Repeatability, reproducibility and short and long-term stability

A repeatability test and a short and long-term stability test was conducted for promising candidate materials. Three batches of materials impregnated with different VOCs were generated. The three batches were divided into small proportions and put into individual amber glass vials. The mass in each vial was chosen in such a way, that the expected VOC release can be well measured in 270 L and 119 L emission test chambers. Three vials, each filled with a respective material, were put together in an air-tight package. A total of 26 packages were produced and stored under different temperatures (–18, 5, 23 and 35 °C) and for different storage times (immediate testing, 0.5, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months). A set of samples was distributed to each partner. Since no influence of the storage conditions was observed, the data from the stability test was used to determine the reproducibility. Additionally, six samples were immediately tested after preparation (repeatability test).

3. Results and discussion

The investigations of the performance of the impregnated materials were carried out with dry and humidified air. Based on these results sample materials were selected for a validation exercise that took place at two different laboratories under the test conditions prescribed in EN 16516. All results are presented in Tables 2 and 3 and discussed in the following.

3.1. Investigations under dry air conditions

The impregnation procedure is conducted without presence of water. Thus, even hygroscopic materials can be impregnated without further adaptation. Humidity has a negative effect on the emission behavior of water sensitive materials. The strong interaction between water and material leads to complete displacement of VOC from the material within a few days. Thus, dry testing conditions must be established when hygroscopic materials are used. Though the goal is to obtain a suitable ERM for standard conditions (i.e., 50 % rel. humidity), studying hygroscopic materials expands the scope of material properties that cannot be found in non-hygroscopic materials. Zeolite 1 was used as a model material to optimize the impregnation parameters. It was used, because of availability and its readily available comprehensive characterization data.

Table 2

Results of measurements of the impregnated porous materials carried out under dry and humid air conditions.

	Entry	Material name	Commercial name	Target compound	ΔER [%] over 14	Emission rate [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}^*\text{g}$]	Emission rate [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}^*\text{g}$]	No. of samples	
					days	at day 14	at day 21		
					Min–Max	Min–Max	Min–Max		
dry air testing	1	Zeolite 1	FD-107	<i>n</i> -heptane	5–33	0.6–10	0.5–10	12	
	2	Zeolite 1	FD-107	<i>n</i> -hexane	5–18	3–25	3–25	4	
	3	Zeolite 1	FD-107	toluene	5–53	2–15	1–12	7	
	4	Zeolite 2	13X APG	<i>n</i> -heptane	5–47	0.2–26	0.2–22	20	
	5	Zeolite 2	13X APG	<i>n</i> -hexane	5–31	2.5–11	2.5–9	5	
	6	Zeolite 2	13X APG	toluene	40–48	1–2.4	0.6–1.5	2	
	7	Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -heptane	28–37	15–19	12–14	2	
	8	AC 1	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	32–34	33–42	26–32	2	
	9	AC 1	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	16–39	32–37	21–33	2	
	10	AC 1	C 40/4	toluene	35–40	53–57	34–41	2	
	11	AC 2	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	29	40	31	1	
	12	AC 2	C 45/4	toluene	16–32	32–49	29–38	2	
	13	AC 3	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	15–38	4–45	4–33	2	
	14	AC 3	C 47/4	toluene	32–33	40–45	30–34	2	
	Humid air testing	15	MOF	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -heptane	34–44	20–55	17–40	4
16		Zeolite 1	FD-107	<i>n</i> -heptane	–	0	0	5	
17		Zeolite 1	FD-107	toluene	–	0	0	1	
18		Zeolite 2	13X APG	toluene	–	0	0	3	
19		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -heptane	30–35	10–14	8–10	2	
20		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -hexane	21–38	18–41	14–29	16	
21		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	toluene	16–42	14–33	12–25	14	
22		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	21–41	13–42	11–29	11	
23		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	butyl acetate	–	0	0	2	
24		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	butyl glycol	30–39	33–237	25–189	3	
25		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	cyclohexanone	35–42	25–52	18–33	3	
26		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	2-ethoxyethanol	35–48	23–59	13–43	3	
27		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	<i>n</i> -hexadecane	1–10	17–95	17–94	3	
28		Zeolite 4	H-BEA-150	methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	28–39	14–35	12–24	3	
29		AC 1	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	14–41	27–61	25–36	3	
30		AC 1	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	22–40	13–77	10–50	20	
31		AC 1	C 40/4	toluene	26–33	21–104	16–66	30	
32		AC 1	C 40/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	24–39	10–39	9–35	12	
33		AC 1	C 40/4	butyl acetate	30–35	67–85	52–59	2	
34		AC 1	C 40/4	butyl glycol	25–30	18–107	15–90	2	
35		AC 1	C 40/4	cyclohexanone	39–41	28–31	19–21	2	
36		AC 1	C 40/4	2-ethoxyethanol	38–39	66–71	49–52	3	
37		AC 1	C 40/4	<i>n</i> -hexadecane	2–34	11–17	8–17	2	
38		AC 1	C 40/4	methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	35–39	22–76	16–54	3	
39		AC 2	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	24–45	32–38	23–27	3	
40		AC 2	C 45/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	41–42	34–59	22–37	2	
41		AC 2	C 45/4	toluene	15–50	26–108	24–59	6	
42		AC 2	C 45/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	32	28	18	1	
43		AC 3	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -heptane	24–44	28–34	21–24	3	
44		AC 3	C 47/4	<i>n</i> -hexane	21–35	13–37	9–29	6	
45		AC 3	C 47/4	toluene	25–39	15–71	13–48	3	
46		AC 3	C 47/4	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	37–46	18–22	11–16	2	
47		MOF	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -heptane	30–37	28–41	17–30	2	
48		MOF	ZIF-8	<i>n</i> -hexane	58	16	5	1	

Table 3

Results of the repeatability test (6 material replicates measured in parallel) and the short and long-term stability test of the candidate emission reference material. The stability tests were carried out independently at two laboratories in parallel for different storage temperatures ([–18, 5, 23, 35] °C) and storage times ([0, 0.5, 3, 6, 12] months). Since no influence of the storage conditions was found, the same data was used to calculate the reproducibility.

Entry	Material	Target compound	Relative repeatability					
			Mean ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}^*\text{g}$] at day 14	RSD [%] at day 14	Mean ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}^*\text{g}$] at day 21	RSD [%] at day 21	Mean ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}^*\text{g}$] at day 28	RSD [%] at day 28
1	AC 1	<i>n</i> -hexane	57.4	10.6	37.0	15.5	24.0	14.5
2	AC 2	toluene	79.0	7.0	54.6	4.7	37.5	3.0
3	AC 1	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	49.0	19.1	36.9	16.5	29.0	18.6
Relative reproducibility								
4	AC 1	<i>n</i> -hexane	58.0	25.6	31.7	24.2	22.1	26.3
5	AC 2	toluene	74.9	19.4	45.3	13.8	30.8	22.8
6	AC 1	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	41.6	27.0	28.3	25.8	21.5	31.8

Relative standard deviation (RSD) is calculated based on the standard deviation divided by the mean value.

Different impregnation parameters were investigated during optimization: temperature, pressure, time and several smaller adaptations (influence of material form [powder vs. granules], CO₂ vs. N₂, dry testing vs. humid testing etc.). No significant effect was found for any of the parameters (besides humidity for hygroscopic materials). The interpretability is impeded, because of the bad repeatability (Table 2, column ΔER), but similar values were found for all kinds of different sets of parameters. The variability remained high as well. It seems, that at least one influential parameter is not known and controlled yet. Part of the optimization was also repeated with several non-hygroscopic materials with similar findings. Thus, the impregnation method was left without changes.

Several measurements revealed that it is possible to obtain a stable emission rate ($\Delta ER \leq 10\%$ over 14 days) with zeolite 1 impregnated with n-heptane, n-hexane and toluene (Table 2, entry 1–3). However, due to the high variability, only a proportion of batches fulfilled this requirement. In case of n-heptane, 15 impregnation attempts were conducted, from which three failed (no visible emission) and 12 successful emission testings were performed. Five of these batches revealed a ΔER of 10% or less. Perhaps, water ingress during sample transfer has a negative influence here. However, the variability can also be high for non-hygroscopic materials (Table 2, entry 9, 20–22 etc.). Very similar results to zeolite 1 were obtained with zeolite 2 impregnated with n-heptane and n-hexane (Table 2, entry 4–5). The duplicate measurements of toluene impregnated zeolite 2 differs (Table 2, entry 6), though ‘outliers’ caused by the high variability cannot be excluded. The reason for the similar emission behaviour could be that zeolite 1 and 2 have similar material properties (Table 1, entry 1–2). Several impregnation attempts were made with zeolite 3, but no emission could be observed afterwards. The pore size (~0.3 nm) of this material is too small for n-hexane and toluene (Table 1, entry 3).

A few dry emission testings were conducted with non-hygroscopic materials as well (Table 2, entry 7–15). Zeolites with a Si/Al ratio ≥ 150 , such as zeolite 4, are quite non-hygroscopic (Table 1, entry 4) (Chen, 1976). The change in composition leads to a change in porosity and polarity. Unfortunately, due to this, zeolite 4 shows worse stabilities of $\Delta ER = 28\text{--}37\%$ (Table 2, entry 7). But in contrast to zeolite 1 and 2, zeolite 4 exhibits the same emission behaviour under dry and humid conditions (Table 2, entry 19). The other non-hygroscopic materials act similar and will be discussed in section 3.2. Though hygroscopic materials cannot be used under standard test conditions, there is potential for use under dry conditions. It was further found that the properties of zeolites 1 and 2 seem to be very beneficial. A non-hygroscopic material with the same pore size and polarity could be a very good candidate material for humid testing conditions. However, since especially the hygroscopicity and the polarity are linked to each other, it is very unlikely to find such a material.

3.2. Investigations under humid air conditions

As explained before, hygroscopic materials do not show a detectable emission under humid air a few days after loading the emission test chamber (Table 2, entry 16–18). However, impregnated non-hygroscopic materials, such as zeolite 4, activated carbons (AC 1–3) or the metal organic framework (MOF), can be tested and show similar results to tests under dry conditions.

Impregnated zeolite 4 exhibits mediocre ΔER values for most VOCs, such as n-hexane, n-heptane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol, butyl glycol, cyclohexanone, 2-ethoxyethanol and MIBK (16–48%, Table 2, entry 19–22, 24–26 and 28). Very good ΔER values were found for n-hexadecane (1–10%, Table 2, entry 27), while the impregnation with butyl acetate did not work (Table 2, entry 23). However, with only two impregnation attempts outliers cannot be ruled out with respect to the high variability.

The activated carbons (AC 1–3) originate from the same base material (hard coal) and have been produced with a similar procedure. Yet,

they possess different surface areas and porosities (Table 1, entry 5–7; see also Fig. S2). It seems, that the stability (ΔER) is not influenced by these two parameters, since similar values were found for all three ACs and the respective VOCs (Table 2, entry 29–46). Mediocre ΔER values (14–50%) were found for all ACs and most VOCs as well. One exemption is n-hexadecane again: very good to mediocre values were found for AC 1 (2–34%, Table 2, entry 37). When comparing the absolute emission rates of AC 3 to AC 1 or AC 2, a trend between higher surface areas and an increase in the emission rate can be recognized (Table 2, column Emission rate at day 14 and 21).

The impregnated MOF also exhibits mediocre values for n-hexane and n-heptane (30–58%, Table 2, entry 47–48). Comparisons between zeolite 4, the ACs and MOF can be hardly made, because often more than one material parameter is changed. The pore size distribution and cylindrical pore form is very uniform for zeolite 4 and MOF, while the ACs have irregular pore sizes and a dominant slit pore form (Wickens, 1990; Moshoeshoe et al., 2017; Bergaoui et al., 2021). Though the general structure of zeolites and the MOF is similar, the pore sizes and polarities are different. Zeolite 4, even with a Si/Al ratio of 150, still possesses at least some polarity, due to the remaining strongly polar Al⁺ ions. The ACs possess little polarity due to their hetero-atom content, and the MOF is polar as well, due to the polar nature of 2-methylimidazol. The order of polarity of the ACs (AC 1 > AC 2 > AC3) can be estimated from the elemental analysis (Table S3).

Two processes must be distinguished, when interpreting the impregnation: (a) the penetration of VOC molecules into the material, which is highly dependent on the smallest opening to the cavities. This is especially critical for zeolites and the sodalite-like MOF that possess an aperture to their bigger cavities (Park et al., 2006). And (b) the adsorption inside of the material, which is dependent on the form, size, volume, and linkage of pores, as well as the interaction of the material and VOC.

The aperture size is not automatically a hard limit for all molecules with a smaller size. Movement (i.e., vibration and rotation) of the lattice and VOC molecules can lead to penetration of even bigger molecules. Furthermore, only the smallest cross-section of a molecule is relevant if penetration can occur or not. The overall size, and its relation to the aperture, are still relevant for diffusion and thus the optimal impregnation parameters. Since emission occurred over a prolonged time for all materials (besides zeolite 3) and VOC molecule size combinations, the aperture size of most materials does not seem to be a hard limit for any of the tested VOCs. But it can be argued, if the impregnation parameters, which were optimised with n-heptane, could be further adapted (i.e., longer impregnation times) for bigger molecule sizes.

The material properties also influence the emission behaviour. While strong interactions between molecule and porous material are beneficial for the impregnation, it can be a hindrance for the release. Mull et al. found that the transport processes at the material-air interface and within the material are highly important for the emission (Mull et al., 2017). Of course, these transport processes are also highly dependent on VOC specific parameters (i.e., partition coefficient, volatility, polarity and molecular size/weight). Thus, a good fit between a specific VOC and a porous material must be found. The rise of tailor-made nano porous materials such as MOFs or zeolites poses great chances for this topic (Lee et al., 2021). In general, it can be hypothesized, that a stabilised emission occurs, when the inner transport is much faster than the outer transport processes. Another advantage might be, when the concentration inside the reservoir does not change over the relevant period. Thus, large pores with a bottleneck and filled with liquid VOC, as well as interconnectivity between the pores might be beneficial for a steady concentration. Another possibility is the use of an additional layer (i.e., coating) around the porous material. The porous core acts as a reservoir, while the coating guarantees a retarded release.

3.3. Results of repeatability, stability and reproducibility tests

Based on preliminary investigations, the materials AC1 and AC2 seemed to be promising for use under realistic test conditions. Three batches of impregnated AC were selected to be tested in-depth: AC1 (granules) impregnated with n-hexane, AC2 (granules) impregnated with toluene and AC1 (granules) impregnated with 2-ethyl-1-hexanol. The test scheme is described in chapter 2.8 and the results are summarised in Table 3.

The repeatability is dependent on the material/VOC combination and point of time of sampling. Initially, the emission is very high and quickly decreases over the first couple of days (Fig. S4, supplement). This is caused by VOC being adsorbed on the surface of the material. Only after the superficial VOC is evaporated, the material shifts towards a stable steady state. Thus, longer testing times usually yield a better repeatability as it can be seen for AC 2 impregnated with toluene (Table 3, entry 2). However, this is only true for well measurable chamber air concentrations. The uncertainty of the analytical device superimposes other factors the closer the concentration comes to the lowest calibration standard (20 ng μL^{-1}). Due to this, AC 1 impregnated with n-hexane has its best repeatability (10.6 %) 14 days after the emission test chamber was loaded and shows similar values after 21 and 28 days (15.5 and 14.5 % respectively) (Table 3, entry 1). AC 1 impregnated with 2-ethyl-1-hexanol has its best repeatability after 21 days (16.5 %) and shows similar values before and after (19.1 and 18.6 % respectively) (Table 3, entry 3). The very good repeatability of AC 2 impregnated with toluene is particularly remarkable.

After storing the materials for different times and under different temperatures, the samples were put into emission test chambers. The emission rate 28 days after loading was used to determine the influence of the storage parameters (Fig. S5, supplement). No trend was found for the storage conditions, so the data from this study was used to calculate the reproducibility (Table 3, entries 4–6). The best reproducibility for all materials was found 21 days after loading the emission test chamber. AC 2 impregnated with toluene had the best value (13.8 %), followed by AC 1 impregnated with n-hexane (24.2 %) and AC 1 impregnated with 2-ethyl-1-hexanol (25.8 %). The very good reproducibility of AC 2 impregnated with toluene is very impressive.

Although, the stability criteria of $\Delta ER \leq 10\%$ could not be achieved for any of the materials measured under humid test conditions, it might be feasible to use impregnated porous materials such as the AC 2 impregnated with toluene as an ERM with a predictable emission behaviour.

4. Conclusions

Impregnated porous materials might be used as ERMs in the future. Our findings indicate the potential of this approach, which is cheap, easy to produce, and easy to handle. So far, one best fit (AC 1/toluene) was found showing a very high in-batch reproducibility. Porous material batches, impregnated with different VOCs, can be combined to a multi-VOC ERM, or used in conjunction with other ERMs. Though one of the main goals for all impregnated porous materials, stable emission was only achieved with zeolite 4/n-hexadecane under humid air, or with the severe limitation of a dry air atmosphere. Further development is needed to broaden the scope of VOCs, find more best fits of material/VOC combinations and improve the impregnation procedure. But even in its current state, it might be possible to produce huge batches of material, store them for at least 12 months and use them for QA/QC purposes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christoph Grimmer: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Matthias Richter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project

administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Thomas Neuhaus:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Carsten Prinz:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Rebecca Skadi Strzelczyk:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Irem Colakoglu:** Formal analysis. **Wolfgang Horn:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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